

DIRECT PURPOSEFUL EXPERIENCE IN ENHANCING THE LANGUAGE SKILLS OF GRADE 6 PUPILS OF BALIC-BALIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOL OF OLONGAPO CITY, PHILIPPINES

Lorie M. Fontecha

Teacher III, Balic-Balic Elementary School, Sta. Rita Olongapo City

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Abstract: Students are encouraged to interact with the subject matter of the class through activities such as discussions, problem-solving, role playing, and case studies, amongst other more hands-on approaches. When compared to passive methods such as lectures and seminars, this method requires a higher level of participation on the part of the learner. It requires student participation that entails meaningful engagement with the material, both on the level of an individual student and on the level of the classroom as a whole. The study aimed to find out the effectiveness of the direct purposeful experiences in the level of language skills of grade 6, Balic-Balic Elementary Schools, S.Y. 2018-2019. Descriptive method was used for quantitative research. Results showed that the level of language skills in terms of grammar in the pre-test is developing. Based on the summary of investigations conducted, it has been conclude that: The level of language skills of the Grade 6 pupil in English in pre-test is improving in terms of grammar and post-test after direct application of direct purposeful experience is Approaching Proficiency.

Keywords: Direct Purposeful Experience, Grammar, Language Skills.

1. INTRODUCTION

Direct purposeful experiences identify different activities under direct purposeful experiences and appreciate importance of hands-on activities. It is also a first-hand experiences that make up the foundation of our learning which include the sensory experiences. The purpose of direct purposeful experiences is to develop higher level thinking skills and serves as the foundation of concept formation, generalization and abstraction that can enhance the language skills of the students. Research has shown that language, the foundations of which are developed by age four has a profound impact on children's preparedness for kindergarten and on their success throughout their academic career. Children typically enter school with a wide range of background knowledge and oral language ability, attributable in part to factors such as children's experiences in the home and their socioeconomic status (Fernald Marchman, & Weisleder, 2013). The resulting gap in academic ability tends to persist or grow throughout their school experience (Fielding, Kerr, & Rosier, 2007; Juel, Biancarosa, Coker & Deffes, 2003), which is why a strong focus on oral language development in the early years is imperative for future academic success. Due to the growing number of diverse profiles of learning needs, the classroom teacher faces the daunting task of providing sufficiently powerful instruction to meet the needs of all students. In order to help close the achievement gap for some of these students, teachers must use effective assessments to identify gaps and then provide instruction that is more intensive than typical instruction to help accelerate learning as stated by Brooke (2017). Through the experiential learning or the direct purposeful experiences approach the student can be able to develop their language ability. Theory of Direct

purposeful experiences as instructional materials is the most real in Dale's Cone of Experience. It focuses on the questions: what do direct purposeful experiences refer to? and where should these direct and purposeful experiences lead the learners? Direct purposeful experiences are the concrete and firsthand experiences that make up the foundation of learning, these are the rich experiences that our senses bring from which we construct the ideas, the concepts, the generalizations that give meaning and order to our lives Dale (1969). Experiential learning is the basic process of learning through experience and is more specifically defined as learning through reflection on doing. It is akin to forms of Hands-on Learning but does not necessarily involve participants reflecting on the outcomes or products of the process. Experiential learning is distinct from traditional forms of rote or didactic learning, in which the learner plays a comparatively passive role. It is related to, but not synonymous with, other forms of action learning and free-choice learning, along with cooperative learning according to Beard (2010). The previous study of Nardo and Hufana (2014) was used by the current researcher to continue to develop learning materials in writing in the course of Bachelor in Elementary Education. The current researcher considers the use of direct purposeful experiences approach for the learning and satisfaction of the students. The students work on their own and the teachers' role are to guide and monitor the progress of the students in doing their individual tasks. With the direct purposeful experiences, students work on various activities that are interesting and challenging enough to maintain focus and attention. These study relative to the experiential learning in enhancing the English language skills of the pupils. Particularly, this research assesses the effectiveness of the direct purposeful experience enhancing the language skills of the grade 6 pupils in Balic-Balic Elementary School of Sta. Rita, Olongapo City.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

Grammatical rule is among other problems found in the process of learning other languages. This truth also applies to those who are learning English in different levels of education. Second language students usually make mistakes in certain grammatical rules. According to the Widianingsih and Gulö (2016) the major kinds of errors made by the students are related to plural markers, articles, verbs, and tenses. In the effort of language learners studying other languages, there have been problems and theories found as well as other issues coming therewith (Lekova, 2010). Thus, dealing with students with this problems at the elementary level brought the present researchers to find out specific grammatical level of skills in learning English as their second language. As cited by *De Valoes* (2014), language impacts the daily lives of members of any race, creed, and region of the world. Language helps express our feelings, desires, and queries to the world around us. Words, gestures and tone are utilized in union to portray a broad spectrum of emotion. The unique and diverse methods human beings can use to communicate through written and spoken language is a large part of what allows to harness our innate ability to form lasting bonds with one another; separating mankind from the rest of the animal kingdom.

Theoretical /Conceptual framework

The theories that were used in this study are Kolb's theory of experiential learning, according to Kolb & Kolb (2009), experiential learning is a process by which knowledge results from different combinations of grasping and transforming experiences. We can grasp experience two different ways; through concrete experience and abstract conceptualization. People can then transform experience in two ways; through reflective observation or active experimentation. This process is often portrayed as a cycle. Kolb's theory of experiential learning also serves as the basis for his four learning styles. Each of the four learning styles is characterized by strengths in two of the four major steps of the learning cycle. People with a converging learning style prefer to learning through abstract conceptualization and active experimentation. Those with a diverging learning style prefer concrete experience and reflective observation. The assimilating style is associated with abstract conceptualization and reflective observation. The accommodating learning style is linked to concrete experience and active experimentation. While learning styles remain a fairly controversial and oft-debated area within psychology and education, Kolb's theory has emerged as one of the most popular and widely used.

Research Design

This research used the descriptive method for quantitative research. It attempts to analyze and assess the role of Direct Purposeful Experiences of the Grade 6 pupils of Balic- Balic Elementary School.

Respondents and Location

The research was conducted in Balic-Balic Elementary School located at Sta.Rita, Olongapo City, S.Y. 2018-2019, The two hundred twenty (220) pupils in Balic-Baic elementary school were chosen as the respondents in giving pre-test and post-test by the researcher.

Below is the map showing the exact location of the research locale.

Figure 1: Map of Olongapo showing the location of Sta. Rita, Olongapo City the locale of the study

Instruments

The questionnaires in the present of examination was submitted to the members of the panel for evaluation. Suggestions and comments for improvement was integrated in the final instruments. The questionnaire contained Pre-test and Post-test with thirty (30) items in Grammar, Context Clues and Idioms, which is to identify the effectiveness of experiential learning on enhancing the language skills of grade 6 pupils.

Data Collection

The researcher sought permission from the administration of Balic-Balic Elementary School for the distribution of the instrument. The researcher allotted 8 weeks for the completion of the study.

Analysis

This study utilized the descriptive tools such as frequency, percentage and weighted means distribution. The entire data gather through the instruments was tallied, tabulated, analyzed and interpreted accordingly. The following are the explanations of the utility of the above mentioned statistical tools of data collection. The following statistical treatments illustrate as follows: **Percentage, Mean, Weighted Average and F-Test Analysis of Variance.**

3. PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

Level of language skills of the Grade 6 pupils in English in pre-test and post-test.

Table 1: Level of Language Skills in English in terms of Grammar

Descriptive Rating	Score	Pre - Test		Post - Test	
		Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Advanced	9 - 10	1	0.45	17	7.73
Proficient	7 - 8	19	8.64	63	28.64
Approaching Proficiency	5 - 6	100	45.45	34	15.45
Developing	3 - 4	75	34.09	106	48.18
Beginning	0 - 2	25	11.36	0	0.00
Total		220	100.00	220	100.00

For the pre-test, out of two hundred twenty (220) respondents, one (1) or 0.45% of the respondents got the score of 9-10 with a descriptive rating of advanced. 19 or 8.64% of the respondents got the score of 7-8 with a descriptive rating of proficient. 100 or 45.45% of the respondents got the score of 5-6 with a descriptive rating of approaching proficiency. 75

or 34.09% of the respondents got the score of 3-4 with a descriptive rating of developing. And 25 or 11.36% of the respondents got the score of 0-2 with a descriptive rating of beginning. The computed average weighted mean is 4.55 with a descriptive rating of developing. These result shows that the respondents competence are not good enough in language skills in English in terms of grammar. For the post - test out of two hundred twenty (220) respondents , twenty one (21) or 9.55% of the respondents got the score of 9-10 with a descriptive rating of Advance. 39 or 17.73% of the respondents got the score of 7-8 with a descriptive rating of Proficient. 105 or 47.73% of the respondents got the score of 5-6 with a descriptive rating of Approaching Proficiency. 55 or 25.00% of the respondents got the score of 3-4 with a descriptive rating of Developing. And 0 or 0% of the respondents got the score of 3-4 with a descriptive rating of Beginning. The computed average weighted mean is 5.74 with a descriptive rating of Approaching Proficiency.

Significant Difference on Level of Language Skills in English in Pre – Test

Table 2

1. T – Test on the Significant Difference on Level of Language Skills in English in Pre – Test

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
Grammar	220	556	4.55	0.68

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit	Decision/ Interpretation
Between Groups	99.10	2	49.55				
Within Groups	470.29	657	0.72	69.22	0.00	3.01	Reject Ho Significant
Total	569.39	659					

There was a significant difference on the level of language skills in English in pre-test towards grammar, context clues and idioms manifested in the computed P. Value of 0.00. The result revealed that the level of language skills in English in pre – test shows how the students got the low score.

Significant Difference on Level of Language Skills in English in Post – Test

Table 3

2. T – Test on the Significant Difference on Level of Language Skills in English in Post - Test

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
Grammar	220	651	5.42	1.08

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit	Decision/ Interpretation
Between Groups	15.78	2	7.89				
Within Groups	544.67	657	0.83	9.52	0.00	3.01	Reject Ho Significant
Total	560.45	659					

There was a significant difference on the level of language skills in English in post-test towards grammar, context clues and idioms manifested in the computed P. Value of 0.00, the direct purposeful experience shows that it has been improved the level of language skills of the students after it applied.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the summary of the investigations conducted, the conclusions arrived at the recommendations offered by the researcher.

Conclusions

Based on the summary of the investigations conducted, it has been concluded that:

The level of language skills of the Grade 6 pupils in English in pre-test is developing in terms of grammar and post test after the application of direct purposeful experience is Approaching Proficiency in terms of grammar.

There is significant difference on level of language skills in English in Pre – Test .

There is significant difference on level of language skills in English in Post – Test.

The level of language skills in English in pre-test and post-test is significant.

Recommendations

Based on the summary of findings and conclusions, the researcher offers the following recommendations:

- Developed a literacy development program for the student in language skills in analyzing or how to use the English grammar correctly.
- Enhanced the thinking skills and motivation of the students in grammar.
- Provide learning materials in English to enhance effective teaching and learning.
- Further research study may be conducted in other districts or locale for verification of results.

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